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OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES FOR ENGINEERING STATISTICS

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that mathematics courses are particularly challenging for engineering students. In the wide range of ways to address this problem, we use digital technologies to develop new approaches for students in order to better understand and apply mathematical concepts. In intensive cooperation between mathematics education and statistics departments, we develop learning materials for the field of probability theory and statistics, which will be used in engineering courses and other fields of study. These materials include interactive applications, instructional videos and digital mathematical tasks. In this contribution, we focus on digital tasks implemented with the assessment system *STACK*, which uses a computer algebra system to evaluate the user input automatically. We elaborate on the potentials of digital mathematical teaching materials, such as the numerous possibilities of automated feedback in digital tasks. One possibility to realize feedback messages is to implement graphical representations of stochastic concepts that can also include interactive elements. This enables students to make adjustments to their solution by interactively exploring the underlying concept. For these features, we make extensive use of the JavaScript library *JSXGraph*. All materials are already being used in courses and evaluated by students with questionnaires and qualitative interviews in order to optimize them.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In engineering studies, mathematics courses take an important part as math skills are needed in the engineering profession. However, mathematics courses are very challenging, especially for beginning students, and in many cases the reason for dropping out [1, pp. 70-71]. Therefore, it is important to address these issues and develop measures to support students in learning mathematics. Taking advantage of the possibilities based on the use of digital media in university teaching, we develop digital materials from the field of statistics in a team of mathematicians and mathematics educators from three German universities. These include three types of materials, namely interactive applications, instructional videos and digital mathematical tasks. The focus on the field of statistics is reasonable as working with data and extracting information from them is required when developing, designing or improving a product or a production process for engineers [2, p. 2]. With the completion of the project, all materials will be made available as Open Educational Resources (OER) free of charge on the state portal ORCA.nrw, so that lecturers and students can use them. Since they will be provided open source, it will also be possible for lecturers to change details or even large parts of the materials to customize them to their courses. To ensure that the materials are designed in a way that they are really helpful to the students, regular evaluation of our work is essential. All of our materials are intended for use in engineering statistics classes. Therefore, it is important to consider the needs of engineering students. For instance, Wolf (2017) points out that there is a desire among engineering students for tasks with engineering applications [3]. Regardless, it is important to provide students with the (mathematical) skills they will need for their future careers. In this respect, Barry and Steele (1993) state that “there is a cornerstone requirement for engineers to model and to be able to solve modelling problems” [4, p. 225]. The four educational objectives they specify in this context include interpreting and solving modelled problems, efficient communication, understanding mathematical models of engineering problems and self-education [4, p. 226]. Thus, it should be the goal of teaching engineering mathematics to promote these skills in order to prepare students for their future careers.

In this paper, we elaborate on the potentials of these digital learning materials for engineering statistics. We do this by explaining our approach to development and by introducing some examples in consideration of a theoretical framework. While all three types of material mentioned above are considered below, the focus is on digital tasks that are implemented using the open-source assessment system *STACK*, especially the versatile possibilities of automated feedback such as providing graphics depending on students' individual answers. In addition, we present the methods we use to evaluate and improve the materials as well as first results from this evaluation. Finally, we discuss the next steps of the project and give an outlook on our further research.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this section, we give a brief overview of some theoretical considerations about digital materials in mathematics education. Furthermore, we introduce the assessment system *STACK* and the technical and didactical possibilities of digital tasks.

2.1 Interactive Applications

In the context of mathematics, we identify *interactive applications* as digital materials that show a graphical representation of one or several specific mathematical objects such as graphs of functions, geometric elements or diagrams. The interactivity is supplemented by giving the user the possibility to influence this graphics, which can be done in various ways: For example, it is possible for users to change the value of a slider, move elements such as points, click on buttons or checkboxes to execute different kinds of actions or entering an expression

into an input field. All these actions lead to a change in the graphics (i.e., the mathematical objects in the graphics). With that in mind, interactive applications provide students with the possibility to explore the mathematics behind phenomena by changing something and then observing the changes in the graphics resulting from this [5, p. 105]. These features can bring benefits to the learning of mathematics according to *discovery learning* [6, 7]. As with any type of learning material, interactive applications should not be given to students without context. It is important to find a good way to integrate them into the students' process of learning. However, this does not necessarily mean that it is inconceivable to use them as part of a self-study. But it is indispensable to make sure that conventions are consistent with those from the associated courses [5, p. 104] and to provide the application not separately, but as a coherent overall package. This should include all necessary information, which interactive action is to be done and what is to be observed. In this context, Alfieri et al. (2011) state that "the effects of unassisted-discovery tasks seem limited, whereas enhanced-discovery tasks requiring learners to be actively engaged and constructive seem optimal" [7, p. 13].

2.2 Instructional Videos

On the internet, there is an immense number of video tutorials on mathematical topics. Google, for example, returns 134 million results when typing in "tutorial mathematics". In this wide range of products, we can find videos of different quality. Ratnayake et al. (2019) developed quality criteria for mathematical videos, that are to be tested with teachers. For example, the videos should be technically correct and well designed [8]. In this context, Mayer et al. (2020) [9] provide some results on the possibilities to increase the effectiveness of instructional videos by introducing some principles. Accordingly, creators should draw graphics by hand (or at least display them little by little) instead of showing them completely at once. Moreover, the speaker should alternately look to the board and to the viewers and activate the audience, for example, by inciting them to summarize the contents for themselves. Finally, the video should be filmed from a first-person perspective when showing a demonstration and should contain subtitles if the video language differs from the viewers' first language. Guo et al. (2014) [10, p. 2] found that shorter videos are more engaging for students and thus recommend to keep instructional videos shorter than six minutes. Beyond that, they state that videos are more engaging when there is a "personal feel" and the speaker's head is displayed when it is convenient. The latter implies that it is not important to set the focus on a professional setting but rather on authenticity. This is supported by the finding that instructors should "speak fairly fast" and "with high enthusiasm" [10, p. 2].

Likewise, Kulgemeyer (2020) supports that videos should meet quality criteria, like, for example, the structure of the video or the adaptation to a group of addressees. He presented science explanation videos to two experimental groups of students, with the one group watching a video that met a predefined set of quality criteria. The other group watched a video that was also scientifically correct but did not meet the quality criteria. The result was that the group that watched the video meeting the quality criteria performed significantly better concerning declarative knowledge on the subsequent test [11].

However, the answers to some questions of design depend on the context. An example is the question if the speaker should be visible in the video. Guo et al. suggest to show the instructor's talking head [10], while other authors make the argument that for videos with explanatory character, the speaker's view can be distracting [12, p. 155].

2.3 Digital Mathematical Tasks using STACK

STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel) is an open source assessment system for digital mathematical questions. It is available as a plugin for the learning management systems Moodle and ILIAS in English and many other languages and

is free of charge [13]. For mathematical tasks, *STACK* has some significant advantages over other assessment systems. First, *STACK* is working with the computer algebra system (CAS) *Maxima* in the background. All answers that students enter into an input field are sent to the CAS. This results in the fact that *STACK* is not only able to compare the given answer to a predefined sample solution, but can also check it for mathematical properties. The CAS also makes it possible to generate random values for a question so that each student gets a different task when opening a test. The second advantage of *STACK* is that it gives creators the option to provide their students with a detailed and differentiated individual feedback. When the feedback is well-conceived and implemented, *STACK* flags the mistakes that students made. In this way, students can be provided with individual feedback messages and with hints that suit them. It is even possible to automatically generate a graphic that depends on a student's solution. In a mathematical context where clearness of abstract concepts is important for learning, this can be a very useful feature. While all of these aspects can reduce the effort lecturers need for correction, this especially applies for tasks where students are asked to give an example of a mathematical object with given properties. These kinds of tasks usually have infinitely many solutions and lecturers would have to check each student answer by hand. Beyond the wide range of feedback options, it is also possible to extend *STACK* using the programming language *JavaScript*. For example, students can be provided with a couple of subtasks after failing to solve the initial task. This was implemented with the aim of increasing student interactivity with feedback on their solutions [14].

3 MATERIALS

In this section, we introduce some examples of our digital materials and illustrate how we tried to address the theoretical considerations mentioned above.

3.1 Interactive Applications

One of the interactive applications deals with the geometric distribution (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Interactive application on the geometric distribution.

Using a slider, students can change a parameter p and observe the changes in the probability mass function $P(X = k) = p(1 - p)^k$, the expected value $E(X) = \frac{1-p}{p}$ and the standard deviation $\sigma(X) = \sqrt{\frac{1-p}{p^2}}$. In order to keep the application clear, the students can display or hide the expected value and the standard deviation by using checkboxes. As the use of the interactive application should be framed, we added an introductory text as well as some tasks such as “What happens when p is close to zero? Give an explanation for your observation”. By clicking on a button “Show possible solution”, a sample solution appears and the students can verify their answer. With the theory of discovery learning [6, 7] in mind, this interactive application can be used as an introduction to the geometric distribution. The application was created using the JavaScript library *JSXGraph* [15].

3.2 Instructional Videos

For the instructional video, we decided to explain the definition of a random variable (see Fig. 2 for screenshots). According to the considerations from the theoretical part, we kept the video short (1:59 minutes). In the first half of the video, a random experiment is performed live by the speaker. In the process, a bag of chocolate beans is opened and the content is sorted by color. After noting the number of the blue chocolate beans on a board, the experiment is repeated with a second bag. The audience sees that the number of the blue beans inside the second bag is different from the number inside the first one. This leads to the formal definition of the term “random variable” and its “realization”. As a compromise concerning the different opinions on the visibility of the speaker in instructional videos, we have opted for the speaker to be visible during intro, outro and explanations and the speaker’s hands to be visible while performing the random experiment. During the formal introduction of the definition in the second part of the video, a set of slides is shown and the speaker is not visible. This combination will hopefully bring in a “personal feel” but will not cause distraction when the formal part is done. The example in the video is chosen so that there is a clear reference to topics of interest of engineering students, namely randomness in production processes.

Figure 2: Screenshots from the video on the definition of random variables.

3.3 Digital Mathematical Tasks using STACK

In order to illustrate some possibilities for digital tasks, one example is given in Figure 3. When failing to solve the task, subtasks will be presented within the same *STACK* question after clicking on a button (Fig. 3, upper screenshot).

The subtask appears as a subproblem of the initial problem and is aimed to foster the students’ understanding of the mathematical concept [14]. When performing this subtask correctly, students can choose if they want to get another subproblem or if they now feel comfortable to try answering the initial question again (Fig. 3, lower screenshot). If they fail answering the subtask, they are provided with an instructional video that should help them. Since this is a fairly new kind of task, we hoped to get some thought-provoking impulses for future development. The task is about voters of a party in an election. In the current version, this

context is not yet directly related to engineering. However, a similar task is currently being planned, which will deal with no-shows in air travel.

Figure 3: Screenshots from the digital task on voters of a party.

Another example illustrating the great potential of automatic and individual feedback that *STACK* provides can be found in Figure 4. The task is about box plots, but instead of calculating the values in order to draw the box plot as usual, a graphic with a box plot is given and the task is to specify a data set which would fit the given box plot. After entering a solution, *STACK* checks if it produces the correct box plot. If this is not the case, a graphic in the feedback shows both the given box plot and the one that results from the proposed data. Thereby, the two box plots can be compared and it is even possible to display dashed lines that help seeing if the values of the box plots differ or not. This task not only illustrates the enormous possibilities of feedback in *STACK* tasks including graphics that directly depend on a given answer. It is also an example of a problem where an inverse calculation has to be performed, requiring a higher level of understanding and preventing the use of a schematic calculation without thinking about the task. As stated in the theoretical section, this kind of task with infinitely many solutions would lead to an immense effort needed for correction – and drawing a graphic for each student like *STACK* does in this example would be almost impossible for lecturers. As for the interactive application on the geometric distribution, the graphics in this task are generated using *JSXGraph*.

This task is planned to be tested in the second run of our interview study along with other materials on descriptive statistics.

4 EVALUATION AND FIRST RESULTS

In order to improve the materials, they are evaluated in different contexts. In this section, we introduce our methodical approach for this evaluation. Afterwards, we present first insights into the results by giving quotes from students and summarizing our impressions.

4.1 Methodological Considerations

The digital materials are used in various courses, including those for engineering, pharmacy, and mathematics students. This is advantageous for several reasons: On the one hand, problems concerning the fit of the materials to the lectures and their (conventional) tasks used can only be uncovered this way and not in studies detached from courses. On the other hand, by using the materials in lectures, a large number of students can be addressed at once. Specifically for designing digital tasks with individual feedback, data is also needed to find out common mistakes made by students. This is an effective way to implement the automatic feedback so that the system recognizes when students have made this mistake.

In the winter semester 20/21, first materials were ready for use. In this paper, we focus on the lecture “Introduction to Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics” (IPS) where a number of digital tasks was tested. This lecture addresses second-year students of mathematics. On the one hand, the focus was on student’s use of the materials, on the other hand it was

Figure 4: Screenshots from the digital task on box plots.

important to find out if lecturers who have not collaborated on the production of materials can still integrate them well into their courses. Especially, this includes different scenarios for implementing the materials in one's course.

In addition to the test of tasks in courses, a qualitative interview study was conducted with $n = 5$ students. The aim is to identify and analyze possible difficulties or ambiguities in order to consequently improve the materials. After testing the materials with students from different disciplines, semi-structured interviews were used. For this purpose, an interview guideline based on Helfferich (2011) [16] was created. It includes questions on content and design-related aspects for each type of material (interactive application, instructional video and digital task). The interviews were recorded, will be transcribed later and analyzed in order to improve the digital materials. In addition to surveying students from different disciplines to adequately address the students' heterogeneity, it is important to include both beginning and advanced students. Furthermore, the participants had different previous experiences with digital learning materials and students with limitations, such as visual impairments, were also included. Each type of material has been the subject of the qualitative interviews, and the analysis of these interviews is yet to be completed. In the following section we present first results, including some quotes from students who have already participated in the interviews. Their significance for our further procedure will be explained thereafter. Below, we present first results from both the test in practice and the qualitative interviews.

4.2 First Results from the Evaluation

As part of the test of digital tasks in the lecture “Introduction to Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics” (IPS), two tasks on the topic of combinatorics were given to students with a style similar to the task on the voters of a party. Through this test, helpful results were obtained. For example, we received a favorable feedback through the anonymous forum of the course: *“Dear IPS team, the self-study task on combinatorics was really terrifically designed! I’m really a combinatorics dummy, but these intermediate steps were so incredibly helpful and helped me so much in understanding. Thank you so much! I would love to see more tasks of this type, this was fun. And by being able to repeat it as many times as you like, you can take breaks in between and let the insights “sink in”. Very nice. Thank you very much and best regards!”*¹. This reinforces our opinion that this type of task can help students learn mathematics and is consistent with the theoretical findings mentioned above (cf. section 2.3). Moreover, the cooperation with the lecturer who was not involved in the production of the materials worked very well. In response to a written inquiry, she wrote: *“The tasks we used received very positive feedback from the students. In my opinion, these tasks are very well suited to enable students to deepen (and thus understand) the theoretical content they have learned during lectures. Especially theoretically weaker students (i.e., those who have a harder time with theory) benefit immensely from the repetition and feedback.”*

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with five students, one of them was an engineering student. On a rather rough level, it can be stated that all materials were well received by the students. Nevertheless, there are some aspects that will be changed in the materials based on these students’ remarks. The interactive application was highly appreciated by the students. An advanced mathematics student said that the interactive graphic would be *“very suitable, especially for students who can’t imagine such things so well, because then you can just visualize it, because that’s missing a bit. There is always a bit of intuition missing”*. To the question whether he now has a better understanding of the geometrical distribution, the engineering student answered: *“Yes, I think with such gimmicks you think differently about something than if you just have some task or something. I find it pleasant. [...] Such a gimmick is always very nice and... yes, it’s just illustrative.”* Only the introductory text, the observation tasks and the sample solutions were criticized by some participants, for example for not being as precise as they would have wished them to be. In the case of the instructional video, the choice of example was considered to be very suitable. One student commented that it would take out the *“seriousness”* of mathematics and that it would take on the role of an *“icebreaker”*. Another student said about the video: *“I liked it very much. Also that it was based on such a nice example. You definitely remember that, and it’s always important to remember things from examples, because then you don’t forget them. And so I would remember it again and again, because you always think about it, about these chocolate beans.”* In general, the length of the video was considered adequate by the students, but some of them would have liked a slower pace when the definition is introduced. The design aspects of the video were not explicitly commented and the video as a whole seemed fairly professional to them with some room for improvement, for example with regard to the sound quality. Likewise, the students appreciated the digital task on the voters of a party. One student would recommend the task: *“It’s just for self practice, get clear again what the binomial distribution is, what it does, etc. Definitely I would recommend it.”* Another student especially liked the idea to provide students with subtasks including the possibility to go back to the initial task: *“And what I find very, very good [...] is that I don’t have to go through all the other intermediate steps here, but can say: “I’d like to try it again now”. And my guess would be that if I mess up again, I’ll be offered this help loop again, where I can click on “I’d like to try more intermediate steps”*

¹All quotes are translated from German to English

if I do it wrong again.” Among the students, there was a little controversy about the length of the feedback messages. Some students identified them as particularly detailed and informative while other students said that they probably would not read the whole text because it was too long.

5 DISCUSSION

First responses from students in interviews reveal some interesting aspects: On the one hand, students point out various benefits of the materials that can also be found in the literature. Examples include the length of the video [10] and the possibility to try things out using the interactive application [6]. On the other hand, students address some points for improvement, like, for example, the audio quality of the video and partly the length of the feedback messages within the digital task. The use of the tasks in the IPS lecture gave us some useful implications on how a cooperation with an external teacher can be organized. The written responses from the lecturer, who was not involved in the creation of the materials, can be considered as a starting point for future implementation of the materials in other courses. However, different scenarios for implementation of the materials in one's courses should be considered in the future.

These and other digital materials will be tested with more students, both in the context of qualitative interviews and courses. Especially, it is also scheduled to survey the students participating in the lectures in a quantitative way using questionnaires. In the questionnaires, both the usage behavior with the individual digital elements and cognitive, motivational and emotional components of learning, for example mathematics performance, motivation and acceptance, are surveyed in a standardized way.

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References

- [1] Ulrich Heublein, Christopher Hutzsch, Jochen Schreiber, Dieter Sommer, and Georg Besuch. Ursachen des studienabbruchs in bachelor-und in herkömmlichen studiengängen. Technical report, HIS Hochschul-Informationen-System GmbH, Hannover, 2010. URL https://www.bildungsserver.de/onlineressource.html?onlineressourcen_id=44422.
- [2] Douglas C. Montgomery and George C. Runger. Applied Statistics and Probability for Engineers, volume 3. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 2003. ISBN 0-471-20454-4.
- [3] Paul Wolf. Anwendungsorientierte Aufgaben für Mathematikveranstaltungen der Ingenieurstudiengänge. Studien zur Hochschuldidaktik und zum Lehren und Lernen mit digitalen Medien in der Mathematik und in der Statistik. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, Wiesbaden, 2017. ISBN 978-3-658-17771-3. doi: 10.1007/978-3-658-17772-0. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-658-17772-0>.
- [4] M. D. J. Barry and N. C. Steele. A core curriculum in mathematics for the european engineer: an overview. International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology, 24(2):223–229, mar 1993. ISSN 0020-739X. doi: 10.

- 1080/0020739930240207. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0020739930240207>.
- [5] Andreas Pallack. Digitale Medien im Mathematikunterricht der Sekundarstufen I + II. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2018. ISBN 978-3-662-47300-9. doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-47301-6. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-662-47301-6>.
- [6] Kripa Sindhu Prasad. Learning mathematics by discovery. Academic Voices: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 1:31–33, jan 1970. ISSN 2091-1106. doi: 10.3126/av.v1i0.5307. URL <https://www.nepjol.info/index.php/AV/article/view/5307>.
- [7] Louis Alfieri, Patricia J. Brooks, Naomi J. Aldrich, and Harriet R. Tenenbaum. Does discovery-based instruction enhance learning? Journal of Educational Psychology, 103(1):1–18, 2011. ISSN 1939-2176. doi: 10.1037/a0021017. URL <http://doi.apa.org/getdoi.cfm?doi=10.1037/a0021017>.
- [8] Iresha Ratnayake, Regina Bruder, Felix Johlke, and Nora Feldt-Caesar. Quality criteria for teachers to choose video tutorials for different learning situations. In EDULEARN19 Proceedings, volume 1, pages 3669–3674, jul 2019. ISBN 9788409120314. doi: 10.21125/edulearn.2019.0957. URL <http://library.iated.org/view/RATNAYAKE2019QUA>.
- [9] Richard E. Mayer, Logan Fiorella, and Andrew Stull. Five ways to increase the effectiveness of instructional video. Educational Technology Research and Development, 68(3):837–852, jun 2020. ISSN 1042-1629. doi: 10.1007/s11423-020-09749-6. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11423-020-09749-6>.
- [10] Philip J. Guo, Juho Kim, and Rob Rubin. How video production affects student engagement. In Proceedings of the first ACM conference on Learning @ scale conference, pages 41–50, New York, NY, USA, mar 2014. ACM. ISBN 9781450326698. doi: 10.1145/2556325.25566239. URL <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2556325.25566239>.
- [11] Christoph Kulgemeyer. A framework of effective science explanation videos informed by criteria for instructional explanations. Research in Science Education, 50:2441–2462, 2020. ISSN 0157-244X. doi: 10.1007/s11165-018-9787-7. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11165-018-9787-7>.
- [12] Jürgen Handke. Handbuch Hochschullehre Digital. Tectum – ein Verlag in der Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft, Baden-Baden, 2020. ISBN 9783828875302. doi: 10.5771/9783828875302. URL <https://www.tectum-elibrary.de/index.php?doi=10.5771/9783828875302>.
- [13] The University of Edinburgh. Stack. URL <https://www.ed.ac.uk/math/stack>.
- [14] Mike Altieri, Jörg Horst, Michael Kallweit, Karin Landefeld, and Malte Persike. Multi-step procedures in stack tasks with adaptive flow control. In Contributions to the 3rd International STACK Conference 2020, 2020. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3944786. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/3944786>.
- [15] Universität Bayreuth. Jsxgraph. URL <https://jsxgraph.uni-bayreuth.de/wp/index.html>.
- [16] Cornelia Helfferich. Die Qualität qualitativer Daten. VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, Wiesbaden, 4 edition, 2011. ISBN 978-3-531-17382-5. doi: 10.1007/978-3-531-92076-4. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-531-92076-4>.